
ELECTRONIC INFORMATION RESOURCES AS CORRELATES OF LIBRARIANS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN FEDERAL UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES IN NORTH-CENTRAL NIGERIA.

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Abstract

The study investigated information resources as correlates of librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in North-Central Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 175 librarians in the eight (8) Federal Universities in North-Central, Nigeria. There was no sampling since the entire population is relatively small and manageable. The researcher developed questionnaires titled "Electronic Information Resources Scale (EIRS)" and "Librarians' Job Performance Questionnaire (LJPQ)" which were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts, two from the Department of Library and Information Science, and one from Measurement and Evaluation in Department of Educational Foundations, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Cronbach alpha method was used for a test of internal consistency of the instruments which yielded coefficients of 0.80 for EIRS and 0.78 for WEQ respectively. The researcher together with eight research assistants collected data for the study using the direct approach method and 98% return was recorded. The research questions were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlational Coefficient and the hypotheses were tested using t-test of correlation. The findings of the study revealed among others that digital reference resources and institutional repository resources had strong relationship with librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north central Nigeria. Also, digital reference resources and institutional repository resources had significant relationship with librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north central Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that University management should formulate formal policy that encourages members of staff and students to deposit their intellectual outputs in institutional repositories to make available electronic information resources to librarians for easy discharge of their duties of preservation, tracking and meeting of information needs of library patrons.

Keywords: Information Resources, Librarians, Job Performance

Introduction

Library is attached to every university to support teaching, learning and research. Oyovwe-Tinuoye and Ogbomo (2022) noted that the university library is a service-oriented division in any university that meet the information needs of different categories of users, including lecturers, non-teaching members of staff, students and researchers. The users of library consult and utilize the available information to improve teaching and learning. Aghadiuno, Ayele and Itodo (2020) opined that teaching and learning in the university requires a well-stocked library with relevant instructional materials and information resources. The responsibilities of providing and managing information resources to support teaching, learning and research within the university environment rest on the shoulders of librarian. Librarians require adequate electronic information resources to effectively discharge their duties.

Electronic information resources are resources that can only be utilized through the use of computer, hand set or any electronic devices to access; they can be accessed on the Internet or CD-ROM respectively. Similarly, Ridwan, Tor and Mohammed (2019) defined electronic information resources as the information objects available in a non-paper format and are accessed through electronic means such as computer devices, CD-ROMs, Internet, databases, and other digital networks. Mukhtar and Maidabino (2021) defined electronic information resources as any source of information encoded and made available for access directly or remotely through the use of computer and other electronic devices accessed via the internet and the CD ROM. These resources can be accessed anywhere but if it is on internet there must be network. Okunola (2021) referred to library electronic information resources as electronically supported information materials subscribed to, licensed or housed in the library or print library materials in electronic formats. Academic libraries subscribe to electronic information resources, and are given license before operation. Operationally, electronic information resources are digital version of text, journal and other materials that could be assessed through the electronic gadgets in the library.

Electronic information resources include databases (online and offline), electronic books, electronic journals, electronic newspapers, electronic research reports and electronic lecture notes. Ridwan, Tor and Mohammed (2019) identified electronic information resources to include: online databases, electronic journals, electronic books, electronic reference sources, CD-ROM databases, online public access catalogues, electronic thesis and dissertation, open educational resources and digital institutional repository. The electronic information resources that this study will concentrate on are digital reference resources and institutional repository resources.

Digital reference resources are online-based question and answer platform that attend to queries of users. Tofi, Agada and Okafor (2020) noted that digital reference resources include AskA services, online chat reference, video conferencing, digital robots, and collaborative digital reference. Adamu, and Iliyasu (2019) identified digital reference resources to include e-dictionaries, e-almanacs, e-encyclopedias, e-yearbooks, e-handbooks, e-guidebooks, e-indexes, and abstracts. The authors added that trained librarian assist to render digital reference service to meet the information need of patrons in electronic format. The digital reference resources are programmed to provide answers to specific questions in a given field of study. Ubogu (2020) noted digital reference resources are the use of digital devices to link library clients with librarians and their information sources. The availability of digital reference resources could reduce the work load of librarians and make them concentrate on other tasks to improve their job performance.

Institutional repository is the digitization of the research output and other relevant document of an organization. Adeyemo and Jamogha (2021) defined institutional repository as a platform for digitally archiving, collecting, preserving and disseminating the intellectual output of a university. Similarly, Ukwoma and Ngulube (2019) opined that an institutional repository (IR) is a database for preserving the local contents such as examination question papers, research publications, working papers and inaugural lectures of academic institution. It is a web-based archive that collects and preserves scholarly works of an institution. Okoroma (2017) noted that an institutional repository helps to manage scholarly materials in digital formats such as e-prints, technical reports, theses and dissertations, data sets, and teaching materials created by the institution and its community members. It promotes open access to research outputs, texts and relevant document of a higher institution which could improve job performance of librarians.

Job performance is work activities carried out by employee of an organization. It is obligatory for librarians to perform their duties effectively, and satisfactorily. Echor and Lohor (2022) defined job performance as the way in which an employee executes tasks according to the prescribed job description. Job performance is the behaviours of employee towards discharging their duties for attainment of organization objectives. Igbolie, Obikeze, Ifejiolor and Muokwue (2021) defined job performance as the act of doing a job. The authors added that job performance is the totality of persons' activities in the course of performing his/her role in an organization. Contextually, job performance is the discharge of statutory responsibilities for attainment of predetermined goals and objectives of academic libraries in universities. All the librarians have duties to perform to contribute towards the achievement of the library objectives and goals.

Job performance of librarians is important for institutions as it leads to the success of the institutions. Librarians' job performance is the execution of different tasks in a situation that allows optimal outcome. Oluwafemi (2021) noted that job performance in library situation is geared towards meeting not only the users' information needs but also a basis or a criterion for promoting staff. It is the librarians or employees ability to achieve the organisation's objectives. Librarians are required to discharge their responsibility and duties for which they are employed for attainment of predetermined goals and objectives of an organization.

Some librarians tend to display undesirable attitude to work in public universities in North Central, Nigeria. To buttress this, Agada and Tofi (2020) observed that some library personnel still exhibit poor attitude towards their work and those they serve which may be due to shortage of facilities in universities in North Central Nigeria. Electronic information services are provided in the electronic section of the libraries in public universities in north-central Nigeria but there are usually weak internet networks to enable students to access them. The demographic variables seem to be associated with different roles, work attitude and expectations which exert influence on their job performance. The study thus, sought to investigate electronic information resources as correlates of librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in North-central Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The information needs of some library users appear to remain unmet probably due to shortage of relevant electronic resources. Kutu and Olajide, (2020) observed that there was inadequate modern information resources in most of the university libraries in North Central, Nigeria which makes prevent librarians from discharging their duties like their contemporary in advanced countries. It also seems that some of the public university libraries in North-

Central Nigeria discovered that electronic information resources are not fully managed by librarians as the electronic libraries remain closed to users during work hours probably poor internet services to access them. Though, internet service is available but the bandwidth is sometimes extremely low. There is always problem of power failure as the electronic libraries are not having their own reliable alternative source of power different from the universities. It is in view of the highlighted problems that the researchers investigated electronic information resources as correlates of librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine electronic information resources as correlates of librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in North-Central Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to find out the;

1. Relationship between digital reference resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.
2. Relationship between institutional repository resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between digital reference resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between institutional repository resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between digital reference resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between institutional repository resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.

Method

Correlation research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 175 librarians in the eight (8) Federal Universities in North-Central, Nigeria. There was no sampling since the entire population is relatively small and manageable. Two sets of instruments titled "Electronic Information Resources Scale (EIRS)" and "Librarians' Job Performance Questionnaire (LJPQ)" were used for data collection. The researcher developed the instruments from the information gathered from literature review and consultation of experts in the field of education.

The first instrument titled ERIS has two Clusters namely: I and II. Cluster I which focused on digital reference resources contained 11 items and Cluster II contained 11 items on institutional repository resources. The second instrument titled LJPSQ contains 18 items which measure librarians' job performance. Each of the two sets of instruments were structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD), weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts, two from the Department of Library and Information Science, and one from Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The internal consistencies of the instruments were determined using Cronbach alpha which yielded co-efficient values of 0.79 and 0.81 for clusters I and II of EIRS with the overall reliability index of 0.80, while coefficient value of 0.78 was obtained for section D, librarians' job performance (LJPQ). The researcher together with eight research assistant librarians administered instruments to librarians. A total of 175 copies of the instruments were distributed, out of which 171 copies were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 98% return rate. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer research questions and t-test of correction to test the hypotheses. For decision on the research questions, the coefficient r and the size of the relationships were interpreted using the correlation coefficient by Alsagr (2021), as follows

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .19	Weak correlation
.20- .39	Fair correlation
.40- .69	Moderate correlation
.70- .89	Strong correlation
-.90- .1.00	Very strong correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p -value is equal to or less than significant value of .05 ($P \leq .05$), the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p -value is greater than the significant value of .05 ($P > 0.5$), the null hypothesis was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between digital reference resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria?

Table 1: Pearson r on Relationship between Digital Reference Resources and Librarians' Job Performance

Variables	N	Digital Reference Resources	Librarians' Job Performance	Remarks
Digital Reference Resources	171	1.00	.790	Strong
Librarians' Job Performance	171	.790	1.00	

Table 1 showed a Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.790. This shows that there is strong positive relationship between digital reference resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria. This indicated that the increase in digital reference resources will strongly improve the job performance of librarians.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between digital reference resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.

Table 2: The Summary of t-test on the Relationship between Digital Reference Resources and Librarians' Job Performance in Federal University Electronic Libraries in North-Central Nigeria

N	R	Df	T	P-value	Remark
171	.790	169	2.35	0.00	Significant

Table 2 shows that at 0.05 level of significance and 169df, the calculated t 2.35 with P-value 0.00 which is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant relationship between digital reference resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between institutional repository resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria?

Table 3: Pearson r on Relationship between Institutional Repository Resources and Librarians' Job Performance

Variables	N	Institutional Repository Resources	Librarians' Job Performance	Remarks
Institutional Repository Resources	171	1.00	.735	Strong
Librarians' Job Performance	171	.785	1.00	

Result of data analysis presented in table 3 showed a Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.785. This shows that there is strong positive relationship between institutional repository resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria. This indicated that the improvement of institutional repository resources will strongly increase the job performance of librarians.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between institutional repository resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.

Table 4: The Summary of t-test on the Relationship between Institutional Repository Resources and Librarians' Job Performance in Federal University Electronic Libraries in North-Central Nigeria

N	R	Df	T	P-value	Remark
171	.785	169	5.76	0.00	Significant

Table 4 shows that at 0.05 level of significance and 169df, the calculated t 5.76 with P-value 0.00 which is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant relationship between institutional repository resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.

Discussion

The finding of the study showed that there is a strong positive relationship between digital reference resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria. This affirmed the finding of Adebola and Otoayele (2021) which revealed among others that a strong positive relationship exists between digital reference resources and job performance of law library personnel. The agreement is associated with the fact that the studies were conducted in university libraries using librarians as the subject of the study. The possible explanation for this finding is that digital reference resources allow for easy retrieval and dissemination of information resources which may account for the strong relationship with job performance of librarians in north-central Nigeria. Librarians use digital reference resources to serve a number of patrons simultaneously which make their work easier and thereby improve their job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria.

Hypothesis test also revealed that there is significant relationship between digital reference resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria. This affirmed the finding of Adebola and Otoayele (2021) which revealed among others that a significant relationship exists between digital reference resources and job performance of law library personnel. The use of digital reference resources among librarians create access to information and foster collaboration among inter-library which might explain the significant relationship with their job performance in north-central Nigeria.

The result of the study revealed that institutional repository resources have a strong positive relationship with librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria. This agreed with the finding of Kutu and Olajide (2020) which noted that there was a strong positive relationship between electronic information resources utilisation and academic librarians' job performance in the selected university libraries. The similarity in participants of the study who are exposed to the same kind of institutional repository resources might be responsible for the agreement in the findings. The possible explanation for this finding is that institutional repository resources allow librarians to simplify the storage, classification and update of material resources which might be connected with their job performance. Also, the institutional repository resources provide platform for librarians to make available wide variety of intellectual outputs of universities to users in different locations without physical being present in the library which could strongly increase their job performance.

The result of the hypothesis revealed that there is significant relationship between institutional repository resources and librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria. This affirmed the finding of Kutu and Olajide (2020) which indicated that there was a significant relationship between electronic information resources utilisation and academic librarians' job performance in the selected university libraries. The institutional repository resources are significantly related with librarians' job performance due to the fact that it allows for automation of their routine duties such as preservation, tracking and making available information resources to users.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that electronic information resources have positive significant relationship with librarians' job performance in federal university electronic libraries in north-central Nigeria. The availability of electronic information

resources is associated with their job performance. The provision of electronic information resources boost the morale and improve the job performance of librarians.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. University management should make available digital reference resources to librarians to enhance their job performance.
2. University management should formulate formal policy that encourages members of staff and students to deposit their intellectual outputs in institutional repositories to make available electronic information resources to librarians for easy discharge of their duties of preservation, tracking and meeting of information needs of library patrons.

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